

ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF DIHYDROFLAVONOLS

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Absorption spectra of 4'-OCH₃, 6-Me-4'-OCH₃ and 7-Me-3'-OCH₃-4'-OCH₃ dihydroflavonols are reported and discussed. The spectra are very similar to that of flavanone. 4'-OCH₃ or 4'-O⁻CH₃ substitution does not alter the nature of the spectrum, because there are not in conjugation with C=O and no additional resonance is possible. Reduction of pyrone double bond inhibits the fluorescence.

No work on absorption or fluorescence spectra of dihydroflavonols is reported so far. However, the absorption spectra of flavanones are reported, flavanone being the basic unit in dihydroflavonol (cf. Aronoff, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1940, 5, 561).

Flavanones are reported to be non-fluorescent, when examined in H₂SO₄ solution and excited by daylight (Sreerama Murti *et al.*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1951, 34A, 319).

The present work was undertaken with a view to ascertaining the effect of the reduction of pyrone double bond in flavones. The resonance in flavanone should be essentially similar to chromone :

In accordance with the fact that the phenyl group, even now, cannot resonate with the rest of the molecule, the spectra of dihydroflavonol and its 4'-OCH₃ derivatives are found to be similar to the flavanone spectrum (see Fig. 1). However, the reduction of the pyrone double bond affects the transition probability to a large extent, which is shown by its much smaller integrated absorption (see for 4'-methoxydihydroflavonol and 4'-methoxyflavone being 47.0 and 74.5 respectively).

Introduction of methyl group at 6-position of 4'-methoxydihydroflavonol shifts the bands to red. The bands at 332, 256 and 224 m μ have oscillator strengths of 0.09, 0.17 and 0.60 respectively. The total integrated absorption increases from 47.0 to 56.5.

Inhibition of fluorescence occurs by the reduction of the pyrone double bond due to significant decrease in resonance. The dihydroflavonols were found to be practically non-fluorescent when excited by hydrogen discharge—6-methyl-4'-methoxy derivative, however, exhibited a very feeble green emission. The same compounds, when examined under comparatively strong Hg emission lines 4,047Å and 3,660Å, exhibited a just perceptible green emission. The resonance being more or less similar to chromones without any hydroxyl, which are non-fluorescent, the same behaviour is to be expected of dihydroflavonols.

Fig. 1

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Absorption measurements were done with a Beckman DU spectrophotometer. Absorption has been measured in neutral, $10^{-4}N\text{-HCl}$, and $10^{-4}N\text{-KOH}$ media; solvent 87% alcohol; concentration, $0.5 \times 10^{-4}M$. For measuring $fe d\nu$ (limits 2,100-5,000 $\text{\AA}$) the area under the absorption curve (ν scale) was measured planimetrically.

The compounds used were pure as judged by their m.p.'s.

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